

THEORY OF CULTURE OF DRUG AND PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE ABUSE

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Abstract

Drug and other psychoactive substances abuse has been a major concern as a social problem across the world, but the place of culture has been overlooked in policy making and laws toward the fight against the abuse. The work examines the synthesis of the key elements of Social Learning Theory, Differential Association Theory and Ecological System Theory as they fused in analysis to postulate how culture theoretically enhances drug and other psychoactive substance abuse. The elements of the theory of culture of drug and psychoactive substance abuse were therefore obtained from the combined elements of the Social Learning Theory, Differential Association Theory and Ecological System Theory. The theory postulates the place, roles, and functions of cultural practices in the enhancement of drug and psychoactive substances.

Keywords: Theory, culture, drug abuse, and psychoactive substances abuse.

Introduction

Cultural values possess the ability to shape individuals' perspectives on substance abuse and their likelihood of experimenting with psychoactive substances (Peters *et al.*, 2024). Substance abuse is interconnected with the cultural values prevalent in every society. Culture has been interpreted from various viewpoints concerning human behaviour and the ability to adjust to the environment in which one resides (Peters, 2019). As stated by Modo (2016), culture constitutes an integrated system of learned behaviours and patterns that are typical of the members of a society. Culture elucidates that individuals within the society acquire human behaviour as a component of their adaptive responsibilities (Peters, 2019). Culture is a complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs and any other capabilities and habits which a man acquired as a member of a given society (Tylor 1871 cited in Modo, 2016). Cultural norms impart moral values that individuals must adopt as members of society. However, certain traditional practices have enabled people to challenge moral limits, leading to a detrimental shift away from established values (Peters, Usoro, Mboho and Ononokpono, 2023).

Modo (2016) further elaborates that culture, in its essence, is a comprehensive system of learned behaviours and established patterns within society. According to Peters (2019), culture facilitates the learning of human behaviour among members of society as part of their adaptive responsibilities. It offers society an inherited code of conduct that serves both as a

component and a function of the overall life system within that society (Peters, 2024). Each culture defines what is deemed morally acceptable for consumption and various uses. To a significant degree, culture shapes the accepted delicacies and beverages across all societies, with the consumption of any substance being either socially endorsed or rejected by its members, based on the socio-cultural values and norms (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017). Alcoholic beverages have played a crucial role in the cultural practices of various peoples for many years (McGovern, 2009).

The consumption of drugs and the abuse of psychoactive substances have developed into a prevalent culture among the residents of riverine regions in Akwa Ibom State (Peters and Bassey, 2020). This situation is exacerbated by the proximity of rivers, creeks, and the Atlantic Ocean, which facilitates interactions with importers of psychoactive drugs and enables the local population to export their own homemade substances. Various events prompt different forms of drug use and abuse among the youth in the riverine areas, leading to a significant reliance on these psychoactive substances in their daily lives (Peters and Bassey, 2020). The growing presence of numerous drug stores and other outlets offering over-the-counter and non-prescription medications has become an acceptable culture in many rural regions of the state, coupled with a low level of awareness and sex education in these communities, and this has resulted in a significant increase in the abuse of conventional drugs (Wilson, Usoroh and Peters, 2020). Low-income countries have developed the culture to face inadequate access to essential medicines in healthcare facilities, inferior quality treatments, regular stock shortages, and less than optimal prescribing and utilisation of medications (Peters, Bassey and Nya, 2020), which often lead to abuse of drugs.

Alcoholic drinks and various illicit substances have been integral to human culture worldwide, indicating the presence of a culture surrounding alcohol and illicit use among different human groups globally (Peters, Bassey, Usoro, and Samuel, 2022). Cultural definitions of what is deemed acceptable in terms of food and beverages establish patterns regarding the use and misuse of alcohol and drugs across all societies. Usoro *et al.*, (2015) suggested that communities, through their cultural practices, dictate what they consider as food and drink. Peters (2024) asserts that culture significantly influences the expectations placed on individuals regarding the challenges that may arise from the misuse of drugs and other substances. It has been found that substance abuse is deeply embedded in the cultural fabric of the people (Peters, 2019). On this backdrop, this theoretical paper analysed the theoretical dimensions of culture as a causal factor to drug and psychoactive substance abuse among societies across the world.

Theoretical Analysis

Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1963)

Social learning theory is a theory of the learning process and social behaviour which proposes that new behaviours can be acquired by observing and imitating others (Miller, 2011). It states that learning is a cognitive process that takes place in a social context and can occur purely through observation or direct instruction, even in the absence of motor reproduction or direct reinforcement (Bandura, 2004). In addition to the observation of behaviour, learning also occurs through the observation of rewards and punishments, a process known as vicarious reinforcement. When a particular behaviour is rewarded regularly, it will most likely persist; conversely, if a particular behaviour is constantly

punished, it will most likely desist (Bandura, 1971). The theory expands on traditional behavioural theories, in which behaviour is governed solely by reinforcements, by placing emphasis on the important roles of various internal processes in the learning individual (Bandura, 1963).

Within this context, Albert Bandura studied learning processes that occurred in interpersonal contexts and were not adequately explained by theories of operant conditioning or existing models of social learning (Bandura, 1971). Specifically, Bandura argued that "the weaknesses of learning approaches that discount the influence of social variables are nowhere more clearly revealed than in their treatment of the acquisition of novel responses." (Bandura, 1963). Skinner's explanation of the acquisition of new responses relied on the process of successive approximation, which required multiple trials, reinforcement for components of behaviour, and gradual change (Renzetti, Curan, and Maier, 2012). Rotter's theory proposed that the likelihood of a behaviour occurring was a function of the subjective expectancy and value of the reinforcement (Chomsky, 1995). This model assumed a hierarchy of existing responses and thus did not (according to Bandura, 2004) account for a response that had not yet been learned. Bandura began to conduct studies of the rapid acquisition of novel behaviours via social observation, the most famous of which were the Bobo Doll experiments.

Social Learning Theory integrated behavioural and cognitive theories of learning to provide a comprehensive model that could account for the wide range of learning experiences that occur in the real world. As initially outlined by Bandura and Walters in 1963 and further detailed in 1977 (Grusec, 1992), key tenets of Social Learning Theory are as follows:

- ❖ Learning is not purely behavioural; rather, it is a cognitive process that takes place in a social context. Learning can occur by observing a behaviour and by observing the consequences of the behaviour (vicarious reinforcement).
- ❖ Learning involves observation, extraction of information from those observations, and making decisions about the performance of the behaviour (observational learning or modelling).
- ❖ Thus, learning can occur without an observable change in behaviour.
- ❖ Reinforcement plays a role in learning but is not entirely responsible for learning.
- ❖ The learner is not a passive recipient of information.
- ❖ Cognition, environment, and behaviour all mutually influence each other (reciprocal determinism).

Observation and Direct Experience

Typical stimulus-response theories rely entirely upon direct experience (of the stimulus) to inform behaviour. Bandura opens up the scope of learning mechanisms by introducing observation as a possibility (Bandura, 1971). He adds to this the ability of modelling – a means by which humans "represent actual outcomes symbolically" (Bandura, 1963). These models, cognitively mediated, allow future consequences to have as much of an impact as actual consequences would in a typical S-R theory. An important factor in Social Learning Theory is the concept of reciprocal determinism. This notion states that just as an individual's behaviour is influenced by the environment, the environment is also influenced by the individual's behaviour (Hull, 1990). In other words, a person's behaviour, environment, and personal qualities all reciprocally influence each other. For example, a

child who plays violent video games will likely influence their peers to play as well, which then encourages the child to play more often (Paik and Comstock, 1994).

Modelling and underlying cognitive processes

Social Learning Theory draws heavily on the concept of modelling as described above. Bandura outlined three types of modelling stimuli: Live models, where a person is demonstrating the desired behaviour. Verbal instruction, in which an individual describes the desired behaviour in detail and instructs the participant in how to engage in the behaviour. Symbolic, in which modelling occurs by means of the media, including movies, television, the Internet, literature, and radio. Stimuli can be either real or fictional characters.

Exactly what information is gleaned from observation is influenced by the type of model, as well as a series of cognitive and behavioural processes, including (Miller, 2011):

Attention: to learn, observers must attend to the modelled behaviour. Experimental studies (Anderson and Bushman, 2001), have found that awareness of what is being learned and the mechanisms of reinforcement greatly boost learning outcomes. Attention is impacted by characteristics of the observer (e.g., perceptual abilities, cognitive abilities, arousal, past performance) and characteristics of the behaviour or event (e.g., relevance, novelty, affective valence, and functional value). In this way, social factors contribute to attention, the prestige of different models affects the relevance and functional value of observation and therefore modulates attention.

Retention: to reproduce an observed behaviour, observers must be able to remember features of the behaviour. Again, this process is influenced by observer characteristics (cognitive capabilities, cognitive rehearsal) and event characteristics (complexity). The cognitive processes underlying retention are described by Bandura as visual and verbal, where verbal descriptions of models are used in more complex scenarios.

Reproduction: by reproduction, Bandura refers not to the propagation of the model but the implementation of it. This requires a degree of cognitive skill and may in some cases require sensorimotor capabilities. Reproduction can be difficult because in the case of behaviours that are reinforced through self-observation (he cites improvement in sports), it can be difficult to observe behaviour well. This can require the input of others to provide self-correcting feedback. Newer studies on feedback (Burgess and Akers, 2011) support this idea by suggesting effective feedback, which would help with observation and correction, improves the performance on participants on tasks.

Motivation: the decision to reproduce (or refrain from reproducing) an observed behaviour is dependent on the motivations and expectations of the observer, including anticipated consequences and internal standards. Bandura's description of motivation is also fundamentally based on environmental and thus social factors, since motivational factors are driven by the functional value of different behaviours in a given environment.

Evolution and Cultural Intelligence

Social Learning Theory has more recently been applied alongside and used to justify the theory of cultural intelligence (Pfohl 1994). The cultural intelligence hypothesis argues that humans possess a set of specific behaviours and skills that allow them to exchange information culturally (Fuhrmann *et al.*, 2014). This hinges on a model of human learning where social learning is key, and humans have selected for traits that maximise opportunities for social learning. The theory builds on extant social theory by suggesting that social

learning abilities, like Bandura's cognitive processes required for modelling, correlate with other forms of intelligence and learning (Rear, 2014). Experimental evidence has shown that humans overimitate behaviour compared to chimpanzees, lending credence to the idea that we have selected for methods of social learning (Uddin *et al.*, 2007). Some academics have suggested that our ability to learn socially and culturally has led to our success as a species (Whiten *et al.*, 2009).

Recent neuroscience research has implicated mirror neurons as a neurophysiological basis for social learning, observational learning, motor cognition, and social cognition (Schalk and Burkart, 2011). Mirror neurons have been heavily linked to social learning in humans. Mirror neurons were first discovered in primates in studies which involved teaching monkeys motor activity tasks. One such study focused on teaching primates to crack nuts with a hammer. When the primate witnessed another individual cracking nuts with a hammer, the mirror neuron systems became activated as the primate learned to use the hammer to crack nuts. However, when the primate was not presented with a social learning opportunity, the mirror neuron systems did not activate and learning did not occur (Uddin *et al.*, 2007). Similar studies with humans also show similar evidence to the human mirror neuron system activating when observing another person perform a physical task. The activation of the mirror neuron system is thought to be critical for the understanding of goal-directed behaviours and understanding their intention. Although still controversial, this provides a direct neurological link to understanding social cognition (Whiten *et al.*, 2009).

Differential Association Theory

Differential association is a crime predictive theory (Glaser, 1960). It can be defined as a process by which individuals come to have differential access to criminal values through interaction with other people. The theory holds that, criminal behaviour is learned in the same way that law-abiding values are learned, and that, this learning activity is accomplished in interactions with others, and the situational definitions we place on the values. The theory can be reduced to the notion that, people become criminals because they associated with, and absorbed pro-criminal definitions. Differential association has attracted more attention, over a longer period of time, than any other criminological theory. According to some scholars, no single idea in modern criminology has had impact on how people reflect on crime as has differential association. In the words of Cressey (1952), differential association is the most outstanding sociological formulation of a general theory of crime causation.

Theoretical Background of Differential Association Theory

Edwin H. Sutherland was one of the sociologists from the famous Chicago school. In the 1920s and 1930s, the study of crime was almost like a tale of one city, Chicago (Tittle *et al.*, 1986). At the University of Chicago, sociologists devoted enormous attention to the study of crime. A general conclusion easily gleaned from these studies is their attribution of crime causation to external factors. Shaw and McKay, for example, attributed crime to social disorganisation. Sutherland criticised Shaw and McKay's concept of social disorganisation as a variable for crime causation, and replaced it with his own term, the differential social organisation. It was through this concept of differential social organisation that Sutherland developed his differential association theory. It is also true from the work of Sutherland that differential association theory was developed in an attempt to explain career criminal behaviour (Tittle *et al.*, 1986).

Sutherland first presented differential association theory in 1939, and in 1947, revised it (Tittle, Burke, and Jackson, 1986). The theory consists of nine principles, as outlined below:

- Criminal behaviour is learned; it is not inherited. With this principle, Sutherland rebuffed the argument that crime was the outcome of social disorganisation. He also rejected the view that, criminals were biologically different from non-criminals. Sutherland sought to explain with this principle that, a person who has not been trained in criminal acts does not invent such acts, just as a child does not make courteous remarks unless they have been socialized as such.
- Criminal behaviour just like abusive behaviour is learned in interaction with others through communication. Sutherland suggested with this principle that, criminal behaviour is acquired through association with others, which also includes communication. The use of communication here refers to the total of interactions. This communication is verbal in many respects but also includes the communication of gestures, often described as nonverbal communication. Sutherland's differential association theory hinges heavily on the notion that delinquency is essentially a learned process.
- The principal part of learning criminal behaviour occurs in intimate groups. Sutherland argued that only small, face-to-face groups influence behaviour. For this reason, he placed enormous emphasis on peer and family groups as the most likely sources of initiation into delinquent values and activities. From this analysis, Sutherland discounted impersonal agencies of communication, such as picture shows and newspapers as part of the process for the initiation into criminality.
- When criminal behaviour is learned, the learning includes (a) techniques, which are sometimes complicated, and sometimes very simple; and (b) the specific direction of motives and drives, rationalisations, and attitudes. By this principle, Sutherland explained the specific items that go into learning criminal behaviour, including the skill (procedure/method), motivation (the driving force), justification (reasoning), and the general behavioural outlook that supports criminality.
- The specific direction of motives and drives are learned from definitions of legal codes as favourable or unfavourable. Again, the learning here is influenced by other people (mainly those with whom one has intimate relations). If such people define the law as deserving/non-deserving to be observed, corresponding attitudes toward the law are learned.
- A person becomes a criminal because of an excess of definitions favourable to the violation of law over definitions unfavourable to the violation of law. This principle can be expressed as a ratio between favourable definitions and unfavourable definitions of the violation of criminal law. If the ratio is toward favourable definitions, violation of the law will be impeded, and if it is toward unfavourable definitions, the person will violate the law.
- Differential association (tendency toward criminality) varies in frequency, duration, priority, and intensity. This means that the earlier in one's life, the longer the time, the more intensely and more frequently people are exposed to a set of attitudes about criminality, the more likely they will become criminals themselves.
- The process of learning criminal behaviour involves the same (all the) mechanisms involved in any other learning. This means that the mechanisms for learning criminal

behaviours are the same as those for noncriminal behaviours/any law-abiding behaviour, and even social skills. However, the content and motive of what is learnt are entirely different in the two situations.

- Both criminal and noncriminal behaviours are expressions of the same needs and values. Put differently, the goals of criminals and noncriminal are usually the same. What is different is the means they adopt to pursue this goal. For instance, thieves generally steal in order to secure money, but honest citizens also work for it.

Since 1947, when differential association theory was reformulated, several attempts have been made to empirically test and or apply the theory to different criminal behaviours (Antwi *et al.*,2010). Perhaps the earliest of these was Donald Cressey's application and verification attempt in 1952. Since then, several studies have been undertaken for empirical clarification (Tittle *et al.*,1986), to test the theory as a hypothesis and to verify the applicability of the theory in relation to specific criminal behaviours (Antwi *et al.*,2010). While many of these studies found empirical application for the main argument of differential association theory, that criminality is learned, and in most cases found the theory to be superior to alternative theories on crime causation and crime prediction, some of these studies have suggested modifications in the principles and even the term “differential association.” Burgess and Akers (1966) have provided a reformulated version of differential association theory with the view to incorporating reinforcement theory. In the process, they reduced the nine principles of differential association theory into seven and renamed the theory as differential association-reinforcement theory of criminal behaviour.

While arguing that there has been renewed interest in differential association, some scholars have also suggested differential identification as a modification to differential association to re-conceptualise Sutherland's theory in role construction and role reconstruction imageries (Antwi *et al.*,2010). In 1960, Daniel Glaser acknowledged that differential association is superior to alternative theories of criminological prediction, but quickly suggested that differential anticipation theory would be more appropriate and adequate than differential association (Glaser, 1960).

Ecological System Theory

Ecological systems theory (also called development in context or human ecology theory) offers a framework through which community psychologists examine individuals' relationships within communities and the wider society (Santrock, 2007). The theory is also commonly referred to as the ecological/systems framework. It identifies five environmental systems with which an individual interacts. The Ecological systems theory was developed by Urie Bronfenbrenner (1979).

The five systems are:

Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory

Source: Google.com (20th January, 2019)

Microsystem: Refers to the institutions and groups that most immediately and directly impact the child's development, including: family, school, religious institutions, neighbourhood, and peers.

Mesosystem: Interconnections between the microsystems, Interactions between the family and teachers, Relationship between the child's peers and the family

Exosystem: Involves links between a social setting in which the individual does not have an active role and the individual's immediate context. For example, a parent's or child's experience at home may be influenced by the other parent's experiences at work. The parent might receive a promotion that requires more travel, which might increase conflict with the other parent and change patterns of interaction with the child.

Macrosystem: Describes the culture in which individuals live. Cultural contexts include developing and industrialised countries, socioeconomic status, poverty, and ethnicity. A child, his or her parent, his or her school, and his or her parent's workplace are all part of a large cultural context. Members of a cultural group share a common identity, heritage, and values. The macrosystem evolves because each successive generation may change the macrosystem, leading to their development in a unique macrosystem (Vander et al., 2007).

Chronosystem: The patterning of environmental events and transitions over the life course, as well as socio-historical circumstances. For example, divorces are one transition. Researchers have found that the negative effects of divorce on children often peak in the first year after the divorce. Two years after the divorce, family interaction is less chaotic and more stable. An example of socio-historical circumstances is the increase in opportunities for women to pursue a career during the last thirty years (Kail and Cavanaugh, 2010). The person's own biology may be considered part of the microsystem; thus the theory has recently sometimes been called the Bio-ecological model.

According to this theoretical construction, each system contains roles, norms and rules which may shape psychological development. For example, an inner-city family faces

many challenges which an affluent family in a gated community does not, and vice versa. The inner-city family is more likely to experience environmental hardships, like crime and squalor. On the other hand, the sheltered family is more likely to lack the nurturing support of extended family (Jeronimu *et al.*, 2014).

Since its publication in 1979, Bronfenbrenner's major statement of this theory, The Ecology of Human Development (Vander Zanden *et al.*, 2007) has had widespread influence on the way psychologists and others approach the study of human beings and their environments (Jeronimus *et al.*, 2014). As a result of his ground-breaking work in human ecology, these environments — from the family to economic and political structures — have come to be viewed as part of the life course from childhood through adulthood.

Toward Theory of Culture of Drug/Psychoactive Substance Abuse

Synthesis of the Social Learning Theory, Differential Association Theory and Ecological System Theory

The following points generalise the synthesis of the Social Learning Theory, Differential Association Theory and Ecological System Theory, which formed the theoretical indices of the culture of drug/psychoactive substance abuse:

- Learning process and social behaviour, which generate new behaviours like drug and psychoactive substances abuse, are acquired by observing and imitating others through cultural practices.
- Individuals come to have differential access to certain behaviours like drug and psychoactive substance abuse through interaction with other people in the process of performing cultural rites.
- Individuals build and develop behaviour like drug and psychoactive substance abuse through relationships within communities and the wider society in which they found themselves.

In summary, the theory of Culture of Drug and Psychoactive Substance Abuse explains that people develop drug and psychoactive substance abuse behaviour through communication or interaction in a learning process as they perform cultural rites as stipulated within the moral codes of their community and society as they grow.

Source: Researcher (2019)

Conclusion

The theory of Culture of Drug and Psychoactive Substance Abuse explain that abuse as a behaviour is learned as other social and criminal behaviour through interactions with age cohort members who are abusers or custodians of cultural rites that enhance drugs and psychoactive substance abuse as part of rites as prescribed by cultural norms of their community or society they find themselves. The paper based its conclusion on the Peters (2019) who posited that the youths within a certain age cohort (culturally defined as young adults and adolescents between the age of 50 years and below - Mkpawawa), and mostly of males, through communication or interaction with other members of the age group, with time develop learned behaviour of drugs and psychoactive substance abuse due to the presence of traditional and cultural acceptability of psychoactive substances as part of traditional requirements for cultural activities.

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